

KOSTANECKI-ROBINSON REACTION. PART I. ACETYLATION OF ORCACETOPHENONE AND ITS MONOMETHYL ETHER.

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Kostanecki acetylation of orcacetophenone and its monomethyl ether gives 4-substituted-C-acylcoumarins. Orcacetophenone on acetylation gives 7-acetoxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin which on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid yields 7-hydroxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin and the latter on treatment with alkali gives 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin, identical with the product obtained on decarboxylation of the Pechmann condensation product of *p*-orsellinic acid with ethyl acetoacetate.

Kostanecki reaction, which consists in heating *o*-hydroxyketones with the sodium salts of fatty acids and anhydrides gives either coumarins or chromones or a mixture of both depending on the ketone, the anhydride and the salt used (Wittig, Bangert and Richter, *Annalen*, 1926, **446**, 155; Bargellini, *Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1925, **2**, 178, 261; Heilbron *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1263; 1934, 1311, 1581; 1936, 295, *et seq.*).

It has been found in general, that using sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, by the introduction of the higher alkyl substituent in the side chain of the hydroxyketone, the tendency towards chromone formation increases (Canter, Curd and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1263; Heilbron, Hey and Lythgoe, *ibid.*, 1934, 1581; Chadha, Mahal and Venkataraman, *ibid.*, 1933, 1459, *et seq.*).

Keeping the *o*-hydroxyketone the same, if the anhydride and the sodium salts of higher acids are taken, like propionic and butyric, then there is a tendency towards coumarin formation (Heilbron, Hey and Lythgoe, *loc. cit.* Chakravarti and Majumdar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 151, *et seq.*).

When benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate or their derivatives are used, the products formed are always flavone derivatives (Allan and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2192, *et seq.*).

With phenylacetic anhydride or acetic anhydride and sodium phenylacetate, the products formed are always 3-phenylcoumarin derivatives in the case of *o*-hydroxy-aryl-methylketones (Bergellini, *loc. cit.*; Venkataraman, *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 918; 1933, 617, 1459, etc.). In the case of ω -substituted *o*-hydroxy-aryl-methylketones, chromones are also formed in a small quantity (Baker and Eastwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2906; Heilbron, Hey

and Lythgoe, *loc. cit.*, Chadha, Mahal and Venkataraman, *loc. cit.*). In the case of *o*-hydroxybenzophenones only 4-phenylcoumarin derivatives are formed (Canter, Martin and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1881; Chadha, Mahal and Venkataraman, *loc. cit.*).

Resacetophenone on heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride yielded 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-3-acetylchromone which is deacetylated to 7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone (Kostanecki and Rozycki, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 102). Kostanecki acetylation of oracetophenone was, therefore, thought of as a method for the synthesis of 7-hydroxy-2 : 5-dimethylchromone which was required for comparison with the product which resulted on decarboxylation of the product obtained on Pechmann condensation of *p*-orsellinic acid with ethyl acetoacetate (Sethna and Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **17**, 211).

Orcacetophenone on heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride gives a product $C_{15}H_{14}O_8$ (A), m.p. 125-26°, which on treatment with alkali affords $C_{11}H_{10}O_8$ (C), m.p. 248-50°. This has been found on direct comparison to be the same as 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (I, R=R'=H) (Sethna and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

The molecular formula of the product (A) differs from that of (C) by $C_4H_4O_2$ which suggests the presence of two acetyl groups, one of which of course must be the *O*-acetyl group, the other being a *C*-acetyl group. Attempts were directed towards the stepwise elimination of the *O*-acetyl and *C*-acetyl groups. Alkali of varying strength fails to give the desired result. However, on treatment of the product (A) with concentrated sulphuric acid a product (B), $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$, m.p. 214°, has been isolated which on treatment with dilute alkali gives (C). Both the products (A and B) give 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones which shows the presence of a *C*-acetyl group. The fact that it is easily split off with alkali as well as the fact that the product (B) gives no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride show that it must be in the pyrone ring. The production of 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (I, R=R'=H) from (B) with the loss of an acetyl group shows that there must be a methyl group in the position 4 after deacetylation. This suggests two alternative structures, 7-hydroxy-3-acetyl-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (II) and 7-hydroxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin (I, R=H; R'=COMe) for (B). The latter structure is provisionally assigned to (B) because there is no conceivable mechanism by means of which the presence of an acetyl group in position 3 can be accounted for. Hence (A) is (I, R=R'=COMe).

It may be noted that the *C*-acetyl group could not be introduced by the action of sodium acetate and acetic anhydride under the conditions of Kostanecki reaction on 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin.

(I)

(II)

The following mechanism is suggested for the formation of 7-acetoxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin.

The first step is the formation of the diacetyl derivative of oracetophenone (i). This is then converted into the β -diketone (ii). The acetyl derivative of the β -diketone (iii) then gives on ring-closure 7-acetoxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin (I, $R = R' = \text{COMe}$)

The monomethyl ether of oracetophenone gives on similar acetylation 7-methoxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin, identical with the methyl ether of (I, $R = \text{H}$; $R' = \text{COMe}$) which on treatment with alkali gives 7-methoxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin, identical with the methyl ether of (I, $R = R' = \text{H}$).

The exclusive formation of a coumarin in the Kostanecki reaction on oracetophenone and its monomethyl ether is a point of interest as the acetylation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones produces either exclusively a chromone or a mixture of chromone and coumarin (Kostanecki and Rozycki, *loc. cit.*, Wittig, Bangert and Richter, *loc. cit.*). The 6-methyl group in oracetophenone, therefore, seems to have a profound influence on the course of the Kostanecki reaction.

Attention may be also drawn to the new technique in which the *O*-acetyl group is hydrolysed with concentrated sulphuric acid which leaves the *C*-acetyl group in the pyrone ring absolutely intact and which is then removed with alkali. This new technique of stepwise elimination of *O*-acyl and *C*-acyl

groups promises to be of use in the isolation of 3-acylchromones, and the work to study the applicability of this method in the synthesis of coumarins and chromones is in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

7-Acetoxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin (I, R = R' = COMe).—Orcacetophenone (10 g.), prepared by Hoesch's method (*Ber.*, 1915, **48**, 1127), sodium acetate (30 g.) and acetic anhydride (100 c.c.) were refluxed in an oil-bath at 180-90° for 8-9 hours. The excess of acetic anhydride was distilled off and the reaction mixture added to water. The solid obtained gave on crystallisation from rectified spirit long woolly needles (6.5 g), m.p. 125-26°. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 5.3. C₁₅H₁₄O₅ requires C, 65.7; H, 5.1 per cent).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone*, prepared from the above product and *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride* as usual, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in tiny yellow needles, m.p. 238-39°. (Found: N, 12.2. C₂₁H₁₈O₈N₄ requires N, 12.3 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin (I, R = H; R' = COMe).—The product (I, R = R' = COMe) (1 g.) was kept for 4 hours with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) and then the reaction mixture added to cold water. The product, which separated, was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny shining needles (0.7 g.), m.p. 214°. It gives no colouration or fluorescence with alkali or concentrated sulphuric acid. It also gives no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 67.1; H, 5.2. C₁₅H₁₂O₄ requires C, 67.2; H, 5.2 per cent).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone*, prepared as usual, was crystallised from rectified spirit in yellow needles, m.p. 250-60° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.0. C₁₉H₁₆O₇N₄ requires N, 13.6 per cent).

The *methyl ether*, prepared as usual by refluxing the acetone solution of (I, R = H; R' = COMe) with fused potassium carbonate and methyl iodide was crystallised from dilute alcohol in long shining needles, m.p. 123-24°. (Found: C, 68.5; H, 5.6. C₁₄H₁₄O₄ requires C, 68.3; H, 5.7 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (I, R = R' = H).—The product (I, R = H; R' = COMe) (1 g.) was shaken up with sodium hydroxide (5%, 15 c.c.) and kept for 3 hours. The product obtained on acidification with hydrochloric acid was crystallised from rectified spirit in stout shining needles (0.7 g.), m.p. 248-50°. Mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethyl coumarin (Sethna and Shah, *loc. cit.*) was not depressed.

Deacetylation can also be effected by refluxing the products (I, R = R' = COMe) and (I, R = H; R' = COMe) with sodium carbonate solution (5.5%) for about 1½ hours. The yield is, however, inferior.

The product (I, R=R'=COMe) on treatment with dilute sodium hydroxide gives directly (I, R=R'=H) and the product (I, R=H; R'=COMe) cannot be isolated.

The *methyl ether*, prepared from the *acetone* solution of (I, R=R'=H) methyl iodide and fused potassium carbonate was crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 117-19°, mixed m.p. with 7-methoxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (Sethna and Shah, *loc. cit.*) was not depressed.

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared as usual, was crystallised from rectified spirit in silky needles, m.p. 119-120°. Mixed m.p. with 7-acetoxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (Sethna and Shah, *loc. cit.*) was not depressed.

With a view to see if the *C*-acetyl group can be introduced in the pyrone ring of (I, R=R'=H) the compound (I, R=R'=H) (0.3 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and sodium acetate (1 g.) for 8 hours at 180-90°. The excess of acetic anhydride was distilled off and the reaction mixture was poured into water. The product obtained on crystallisation from dilute alcohol gave silky needles, m.p. 119-20°. Mixed m.p. with the above acetyl derivative from (I, R=R'=H) was not depressed, Mixed m.p. with the product (I, R=R'=COMe) was depressed by 15°.

Acetylation of Orcacetophenone Monomethyl Ether: 7-Methoxy-4-aceto-methyl-5-methylcoumarin.—Orcacetophenone monomethyl ether (2 g.), sodium acetate (6 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) were refluxed for 8 hours at 180-90°. The product obtained on crystallisation from rectified spirit gave glistening needles, m.p. 122-23°. Mixed m.p. with the methyl ether of 7-hydroxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin was the same.

This methyl ether (0.5 g.) was kept in contact with sodium hydroxide (5%; 10 c.c.) for 3 hours. The product, obtained on acidification, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 117-19°. Mixed m.p. with 7-methoxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (*loc. cit.*) was the same.

All the analyses recorded are micro-analyses.

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